

Supplementary Material for: Multistate Models of Valproic Acid Developmental Toxicity in the Zebrafish Embryo

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Section 1 – Experimental data

Table S1. Codes of effects recorded in the Zebrafish Embryo Acute Toxicity (FET) test.

Code string	Meaning
*	Outlier (for technical reasons)
N	Normal development
HA	Hatched
C	Coagulation
TA	Tail attached
GA	Gastrulation arrest
S	Somite malformation
H-	Reduced heart beat
H=	Severely reduced heart beat
H	Missing heart beat
B	Blood pooling
BD	Delayed body development
BL(P)-	Reduced blood flow with pooling at yolk
BL(P)=	Severely reduced blood flow with pooling at yolk
BL(P)	Missing blood flow with pooling at yolk
BL-	Reduced blood flow
BL=	Severely reduced blood flow
BL	Missing blood flow
BR	Visible brain
CH	Chorda unclear
DY	Dark yolk
E	Edema
PE	Pericardial edema
YE	Yolk edema
EB	Eyes larger than usual
ED-	Reduced eye development
ED=	Severely reduced eye development
ED	Missing eye development
EP-	Reduced eye pigmentation
EP=	Severely reduced eye pigmentation
EP	Missing eye pigmentation
FM	Missing face

Code string	Meaning
FU	Fin underdeveloped
GA	Gastrulation arrest
HD	Head deformed
HZ	Head tremor/twitching
JD	Craniofacial deformation
L	Lordosis
KY	Kyphosis
SC	Scoliosis
M	Motionless
MD	Muscle development/ boundaries unclear
NH	Not hatched
O	Otolith development impacted
P-	Reduced pigmentation
P=	Severely reduced pigmentation
P	Missing pigmentation
PF	Pectoral fins not moving
PFA	Pectoral fins attached
PFD	Pectoral fins deformed
SL	Side lying
SM	Spontaneous movement missing
TD	Tailfin decomposing
TF	Tailfin development impacted
YD	Yolk deformation
YR	Reduced yolk resorption
Z	Tremor/twitching

Table S2. Water pH after addition of valproic acid (VPA) at various test concentrations. At the highest concentration, all embryos died within a few hours. Prior to the addition of the test compound, water was adjusted at pH 7.75 (± 0.02).

VPA concentration (μM)	pH
800	5.11
400	6.23
200	6.83
100	7.11
50	7.32
25	7.41
12.5	7.55
6.25	7.64

Figure S1. Internal concentration (ranging from 0 to 1.6×10^{-2} M) as a function of the nominal concentration (ranging from 6.25×10^{-6} to 4×10^{-4} M) and the time (from 0 to 5 days).

Section 2 – Hatching rate modeling

We tested five sub-models linking $q_{N,H}(t)$ and time to fit the data reasonably well. We only used the data of the control group and a three-state model, considering only normal, hatched, and malformed or coagulated embryos, because in the control group the latter state is rarely observed, and hatching occurs most of the time. In that group we therefore have quite clean observations of the hatching process alone. The model structure is illustrated in Figure S2, below.

Figure S2. Schematic representation of the three-state model for zebrafish embryo hatching. States are: “normal” (pre-hatching, N), “hatched” (H), and “all malformed or coagulated embryos” (EC).

The five sub-models describing $q_{N,H}(t)$ time-dependence were:

- A constant rate model (*a priori* probably wrong), with two parameters to estimate ($q_{N,H}$ and $q_{N,EC}$)
- A piecewise constant model with a fixed hatching time at 48 hpf, with two parameters to estimate ($q_{N,H}$ after 48 hpf and $q_{N,EC}$; $q_{N,H}$ before 48 hpf was set to zero)
- A piecewise constant model with variable hatching time t_h , making three parameters to estimate (t_h , $q_{N,H}$ after t_h , and $q_{N,EC}$; $q_{N,H}$ before t_h being null)
- A Hill’s model such that the transition rate $q_{N,H}(t)$ is given by:

$$q_{N,H}(t) = \frac{q_{N,H,max} \times t^n}{t_{50}^n + t^n} \quad (S1)$$

where $q_{N,H,max}$ is the maximum transition intensity from normal to hatched, t_{50} is the time at which the transition rate is equal to 50% of its maximum value, and n is the Hill’s exponent. Those three parameters and $q_{N,EC}$ were to be estimated.

- A Gaussian-form model, reaching a maximum and then decaying, so that $q_{N,H}(t)$ is given by:

$$q_{N,H}(t) = \frac{A}{s} \times e^{\left(\frac{t-t_h}{s}\right)^2} \quad (\text{S2})$$

where t_h is the mean hatching time, s its spread, and A/s the maximum rate, so four parameters were estimated: t_h , s , A , and $q_{N,EC}$.

To choose between those models based on their fit to the data, we used the Akaike information criterion (AIC). It uses the maximum likelihood, $\widehat{L}_{i,j}$, as a measure of goodness-of-fit, penalized by the number k of estimated parameters (Evans, 2019):

$$AIC = -2 \times \ln(\widehat{L}_{i,j}) + 2 \times k \quad (\text{S3})$$

The model with the lowest AIC should be preferred.

The posterior distribution of parameters obtained by MCMC calibration with the embryo transition count data, are summarized for each model in Table S4. The AIC values were 570 for the constant model, 287 for the piecewise constant model with fixed hatching time, 269 for the piecewise constant model with estimated hatching time, 269 for the Hill's model, and 276 for the Gaussian model. The piecewise constant model with estimated hatching time was therefore the best model according to the AIC and was selected (they all give practically the same fit, but it is essentially the most parsimonious).

In the five-state model (Figure 3 of the main text), hatching can happen to normal embryos (state N) and malformed embryos (state E). The piecewise constant sub-model with estimated hatching time was therefore used for both $q_{N,H}$ and $q_{E,EH}$ hatching intensities in the final model.

Table S3. Posterior mean, standard deviation (SD), 95% credibility intervals (IC95%) and maximum posterior (MP) value of the parameters for the five hatching rate sub-model in control embryos.

Parameter	Mean \pm SD	IC 95%	MP	\hat{R}
Constant transition rate				
$q_{N,H}$	0.35 ± 0.033	[0.29 ; 0.41]	0.34	1
$q_{N,EC}$	0.037 ± 0.020	[0.019 ; 0.061]	0.033	1
Hatching rate piecewise constant with fixed hatching time				
$q_{N,H}$	1.3 ± 0.13	[1.0 ; 1.6]	1.3	1
$q_{N,EC}$	0.038 ± 0.024	[0.019 ; 0.061]	0.034	1
Hatching rate piecewise constant with estimated hatching time				
$q_{N,H}$	3.3 ± 0.86	[2.0 ; 5.3]	3.2	1
$q_{N,EC}$	0.035 ± 0.012	[0.018 ; 0.058]	0.032	1
t_h (day)	2.7 ± 0.090	[2.5 ; 2.8]	2.7	1
Hatching rate following a Hill function				
$q_{N,Hmax}$	7.2 ± 2.7	[3.0 ; 13]	9.0	1
$q_{N,EC}$	0.036 ± 0.010	[0.019 ; 0.059]	0.034	1
n	6.2 ± 1.6	[3.6 ; 9.5]	4.9	1
x	3.4 ± 0.35	[2.7 ; 4.0]	3.8	1
Hatching rate following a Gaussian function				
$q_{N,EC}$	0.036 ± 0.010	[0.019 ; 0.059]	0.034	1
s	0.89 ± 0.14	[0.64 ; 1.2]	0.82	1
A	5.8 ± 1.9	[2.9 ; 9.6]	4.4	1
t_h (day)	3.8 ± 0.23	[3.5 ; 4.3]	3.7	1

Figure S3 shows the transition number of zebrafish embryos from “N” to “N”, “EC”, and “H” states, for the five hatching sub-models, as a function of the time (day). Except for the constant intensity model, the data are reasonably well fitted. Figure S4 shows the models’ predictions of time evolution of embryo counts in each of the three state.

Figure S3. Number of transitions between states N , EC and H , as a function of time. Hatching was modeled by (1) a constant intensity sub-model, (2) a piecewise constant model with fixed 48 hpf hatching time, (3) a piecewise constant model with estimated hatching time, (4) a Hill's model, and (5) a Gaussian model. The dots are data, and the lines predictions. The blue, red and green areas are the 95% confidence interval of transition number from N to N , from N to EC , and from N to H .

Figure S4. Fish count in states N , EC and H , as a function of time. Hatching was modeled by (1) a constant intensity sub-model, (2) a piecewise constant model with fixed 48 hpf hatching time, (3) a piecewise constant model with estimated hatching time, (4) a Hill's model, and (5) a Gaussian model. The dots are data, and the lines predictions. The blue, red and green areas are the 95% confidence interval of Fish count in states N , EC and H .

Figure S3 shows the hatching intensity $q_{N,H}(t)$ according to the various models, except for the constant rate model that poorly fitted the data. The profiles are very different according to the model used, but it note that all models pass by the point (2.7, 3.3), which seems pivotal for a reasonable description of the data. There is a large uncertainty about the later part of the curve for the two most complex models, because after day 3 there are very few non-hatched fish left to inform the exact shape of the curve.

Figure S3. Shape of the time-dependent hatching intensity with the piecewise constant with estimated hatching time (green), the piecewise constant with fixed hatching time (blue), the Gaussian (orange), and the Hill's (red) three-state model. The colored areas are the 95% credibility interval of hatching intensity estimates. The thick lines are the maximum posterior hatching rate functions.

Section 3 – Coupled PPBK-multistate model results

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Table S4. Observed and predicted value of transition number for each day and concentration. The most unexpected observations (according to the model) are in bold font.

Concentration (μM)	Observations					Predictions				
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5
<i>Transition N→N</i>										
0	117	112	42	1	0	116.6	113.2	45	1.7	0.07
6.25	60	53	24	0	0	57.8	55.5	22.3	0.79	0.38
12.5	60	58	26	0	0	57.7	55.2	21	0.77	0.03
25	59	55	24	0	0	57.4	54.5	25.1	0.89	0.04
50	59	54	31	1	1	57.2	53.8	26.8	0.95	0.043
100	57	50	25	0	0	56.2	51.3	24.1	0.82	0.038
200	50	38	19	0	0	52.5	41.6	25.6	0.76	0.034
400	0	0	0	0	0	3.5×10^{-2}	6.4×10^{-6}	1.4×10^{-6}	9.2×10^{-7}	9.1×10^{-6}
<i>Transition N→C</i>										
0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4×10^{-2}	1.3×10^{-2}	1.2×10^{-2}	1.6×10^{-3}	6.8×10^{-5}
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	0.03	0.04	0.038	0.0053	0.00026
12.5	0	0	0	0	0	0.035	0.048	0.044	0.0054	0.00021
25	1	0	0	0	0	0.045	0.063	0.061	0.0095	0.00043
50	1	0	0	0	0	0.054	0.077	0.075	0.012	0.00057
100	0	0	0	0	0	0.086	0.13	0.12	0.019	0.0009
200	0	0	0	0	0	0.18	0.29	0.26	0.055	0.0025
400	0	0	0	0	0	2.7	0.0031	0.00093	0.00056	0.00049
<i>Transition N→E</i>										
0	3	5	0	0	0	3.5	3.4	2.4	0.19	0.0082
6.25	0	7	0	0	0	2.2	2.4	1.9	0.19	0.0091
12.5	0	2	1	0	0	2.4	2.6	1.2	0.058	0.0022
25	0	4	0	0	0	2.6	2.9	2.3	0.22	0.0099
50	0	5	4	0	0	2.9	3.3	2.7	0.27	0.012
100	3	7	3	1	0	3.8	4.8	3.8	0.35	0.016
200	10	12	14	4	0	7.4	10.6	8.7	0.90	0.041
400	60	0	0	0	0	57.4	0.032	0.0092	0.0053	0.0048
<i>Transition N→H</i>										
0	0	0	70	38	5	0	0	66.9	44	1.9
6.25	0	0	29	25	0	0	0	31.9	21.9	1
12.5	0	0	30	25	0	0	0	32.7	20.3	0.78
25	0	0	31	24	0	0	0	27.3	23.6	1
50	0	0	18	22	0	0	0	24.4	23	1
100	0	0	15	14	0	0	0	18.8	6.9	0.31
200	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	4.1	0.74	0.035
400	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9×10^{-6}	1.2×10^{-5}	1.3×10^{-5}
<i>Transition N→EH</i>										
0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0.55	0.16	0.0067
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.21	0.13	0.0066
12.5	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1.1	0.40	0.016
25	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.6	1.3	0.059
50	0	0	1	8	0	0	0	0.9	3.5	0.16
100	0	0	7	10	0	0	0	5.6	17.1	0.79
200	0	0	1	15	0	0	0	4.3	25.2	1.12
400	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00028	0.0011	0.00095

Concentration (μM)	Observations					Predictions				
<i>Transition E→C</i>										
0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00021	0.0075	0.011	0.0070	0.0019
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	0.00041	0.012	0.021	0.019	0.0085
12.5	0	0	0	0	0	0.00046	0.015	0.024	0.0066	0.00052
25	0	0	0	0	0	0.00055	0.02	0.036	0.028	0.01
50	0	0	0	0	0	0.00062	0.026	0.048	0.039	0.014
100	0	0	0	0	2	0.00089	0.051	0.10	0.081	0.028
200	0	0	0	0	0	0.0015	0.18	0.42	0.35	0.11
400	0	1	1	18	0	0.006	5.1	4.7	3.9	2.9
<i>Transition E→N</i>										
0	0	0	0	0	0	0.045	1.6	1.1	0.31	0.085
6.25	0	0	1	0	0	0.041	0.90	0.67	0.3	0.13
12.5	0	0	0	0	0	0.041	0.92	0.62	0.054	0.0042
25	0	0	2	0	0	0.039	0.96	0.84	0.27	0.092
50	0	0	0	0	0	0.038	1	0.95	0.3	0.11
100	0	0	0	0	0	0.034	1.1	1.1	0.34	0.11
200	0	4	0	0	0	0.025	1.3	2.1	0.48	0.16
400	0	0	0	0	0	5.6×10^{-5}	0.01	0.0069	0.0063	0.054
<i>Transition E→E</i>										
0	0	3	4	2	2	0.055	1.9	2.3	1.1	0.31
6.25	0	0	4	0	0	0.058	1.4	2	1.6	0.72
12.5	0	0	0	0	0	0.059	1.5	1.2	0.14	0.011
25	0	0	1	1	1	0.060	1.7	2.5	1.5	0.51
50	0	0	1	1	0	0.062	1.9	2.9	1.8	0.64
100	0	3	4	3	0	0.065	2.7	4.5	2.5	0.84
200	0	6	16	2	3	0.073	6	12	6	2
400	0	59	57	34	29	0.094	52.4	46.3	36.4	28.6
<i>Transition E→H</i>										
0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	1.3	1.7	0.47
6.25	0	0	2	4	0	0	0	0.8	1.2	0.55
12.5	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0.90	0.84	0.066
25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.81	1.4	0.49
50	0	0	3	2	0	0	0	0.78	1.51	0.54
100	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0.79	1	0.35
200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.34	0.40	0.14
400	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.015	0.069	0.065
<i>Transition E→EH</i>										
0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0.61	1.6	0.44
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.23	0.81	0.37
12.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2	1.4	0.11
25	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.45	1.7	0.58
50	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0.47	2.1	0.74
100	0	0	4	4	2	0	0	1	4.4	1.5
200	0	0	2	28	3	0	0	1.3	13.9	4.5
400	0	0	1	5	5	0	0	1.4	6	4.7
<i>Transition H→H</i>										
0	0	0	0	72	106	0.1	0.14	0.16	68.4	114.5
6.25	0	0	0	31	60	0.1	0.14	0.16	32.7	55.7
12.5	0	0	0	31	57	0.1	0.13	0.16	33.4	54.7
25	0	0	0	31	55	0.099	0.13	0.14	26.6	48.7
50	0	0	0	16	34	0.097	0.12	0.12	21.3	38.5
100	0	0	0	3	2	0.071	0.031	0.012	4	2.6
200	0	0	0	0	0	0.0032	0.00014	0.00010	0.098	0.032
400	0	0	0	0	0	1.1×10^{-3}	2.5×10^{-5}	2.4×10^{-5}	1.9×10^{-4}	1.1×10^{-3}

Concentration (μM)	Observations					Predictions				
<i>Transition H\rightarrowEH</i>										
0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	6.5×10^{-5}	3.4×10^{-4}	5.5×10^{-4}	0.14	0.25
12.5	0	0	0	1	0	0.00018	0.00096	0.0015	0.4	0.7
25	0	0	0	0	0	0.00096	0.0049	0.0075	1.7	3.2
50	0	0	0	5	6	0.0028	0.013	0.019	4	7.7
100	0	0	0	14	15	0.029	0.066	0.038	15.6	10.3
200	0	0	0	8	0	0.097	0.006	0.0046	4.4	1.3
400	0	0	0	0	0	0.099	0.0023	0.0021	0.016	0.085
<i>Transition EH\rightarrowH</i>										
0	0	0	0	0	3	0.036	0.023	0.015	0.43	0.9
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	0.036	0.023	0.015	0.17	0.49
12.5	0	0	0	0	3	0.035	0.023	0.015	0.83	1.3
25	0	0	0	0	2	0.035	0.023	0.016	0.37	1.8
50	0	0	0	0	9	0.034	0.022	0.019	0.45	3.3
100	0	0	0	0	2	0.027	0.018	0.023	0.96	6.1
200	0	0	0	0	0	0.003	0.0045	0.0043	0.13	1.1
400	0	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.0021	0.0022	0.018	0.095
<i>Transition EH\rightarrowEH</i>										
0	0	0	0	1	3	0.064	0.041	0.026	0.76	1.6
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	0.064	0.042	0.027	0.3	0.9
12.5	0	0	0	1	0	0.065	0.042	0.028	1.5	2.4
25	0	0	0	1	1	0.065	0.043	0.032	0.72	3.5
50	0	0	0	2	8	0.66	0.046	0.04	0.98	7.2
100	0	0	0	11	37	0.073	0.084	0.13	5.8	36.8
200	0	0	0	3	54	0.097	0.19	0.19	5.7	48
400	0	0	0	1	6	0.099	0.20	0.20	1.6	7.5

Table S5. Mean, standard deviation (SD), 95% confidence intervals (IC95%) and maximum posterior (MP) value for concentration-group-specific estimates of $q_{E,EH}$, $q_{N,H}$, and t_h .

Parameter (0 μM)	Mean \pm SD	IC 95%	MP	\hat{R}
Concentration 0 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	0.79 \pm 0.32	[0.32 ; 1.5]	0.83	1
$q_{N,H}$	3.8 \pm 0.62	[2.8 ; 5.3]	3.3	1
t_h	2.7 \pm 0.049	[2.6 ; 2.8]	2.7	1
Concentration 6.25 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	0.82 \pm 0.60	[0.15 ; 2.4]	0.40	1
$q_{N,H}$	4.2 \pm 1.1	[2.9 ; 7.1]	3.4	1
t_h	2.8 \pm 0.049	[2.7 ; 2.9]	2.7	1
Concentration 12.5 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	1.6 \pm 1.4	[0.29 ; 5.0]	2.4	1
$q_{N,H}$	4.1 \pm 1.0	[2.8 ; 6.5]	3.3	1
t_h	2.8 \pm 0.050	[2.7 ; 2.9]	2.7	1
Concentration 25 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	0.71 \pm 0.39	[0.19 ; 1.7]	0.74	1
$q_{N,H}$	4.0 \pm 0.93	[2.8 ; 6.4]	3.3	1
t_h	2.8 \pm 0.050	[2.7 ; 2.9]	2.8	1
Concentration 50 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	1.4 \pm 0.65	[0.48 ; 3.0]	0.74	1
$q_{N,H}$	3.4 \pm 0.56	[2.3 ; 4.6]	3.3	1
t_h	2.8 \pm 0.039	[2.7 ; 2.9]	2.8	1
Concentration 100 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	1.1 \pm 0.38	[0.47 ; 2.0]	0.86	1
$q_{N,H}$	3.4 \pm 0.59	[2.3 ; 4.7]	3.4	1
t_h	2.8 \pm 0.045	[2.7 ; 2.9]	2.8	1
Concentration 200 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	1.4 \pm 0.30	[0.87 ; 2.1]	1.0	1
$q_{N,H}$	3.8 \pm 0.86	[2.6 ; 5.9]	3.4	1
t_h	2.9 \pm 0.025	[2.9 ; 3.0]	2.9	1
Concentration 400 μM				
$q_{E,EH}$	0.17 \pm 0.045	[0.094 ; 0.27]	0.15	1
$q_{N,H}$	3.9 \pm 1.2	[2.2 ; 7.1]	3.3	1
t_h	2.8 \pm 0.077	[2.7 ; 3.0]	2.8	1

Figure S6. Comparison of the final sub-models of transition intensities (calibrated with **all** the transition counts data) as functions of internal concentration (lines and shaded areas) with the separate (concentration by concentration) estimates of the same intensities (squares: MPV estimates; diamonds: mean estimates with 95% credibility intervals). Individual estimates are very uncertain at low concentrations because of low event counts.

Figure S7. Correlations between parameter estimates.

Figure S8. Observed (dots) and predicted (lines) number of transitions between states normal (N), hatched (H), malformed (E), hatched with effects (EH) and coagulated (C), as a function of time for the exposure concentrations 0 and 400 μM . Hatching rate is modeled by a piecewise constant intensity with estimated hatching time. The colored bands give the predictions' 95% confidence intervals.

Figure S9. Counts of embryos in the five states, as a function of time and VPA concentrations. The dots are the data, the lines are model predictions. The colored bands give the predictions' 95% confidence intervals.

Section 4 – Calculation of reference toxicity values

The transition intensities do not depend directly on time, if we take them as functions of internal concentration (Eqs. 28 to 33). In that case, given the posterior distribution of the parameters of those equations it is easy, by mathematical inversion, to compute the distributions of the reference toxicity values of interest. According to Equations 28 to 33 of the main text, the EC_{10} values for $q_{E,N}$, $q_{EH,H}$, $q_{N,E}$, $q_{N,C}$, $q_{E,C}$, and $q_{H,EH}$ – respectively, $EC_{10}(q_{E,N})$, $EC_{10}(q_{EH,H})$, $EC_{10}(q_{N,E})$, $EC_{10}(q_{N,C})$, $EC_{10}(q_{E,C})$, and $EC_{10}(q_{H,EH})$ – are given by:

$$q_{i,j}(EC_{10}) = 1.1 \times q_{i,j}(0) \quad (S4)$$

if exposure increases the transition intensity, or

$$q_{i,j}(EC_{10}) = 0.9 \times q_{i,j}(0) \quad (S5)$$

otherwise.

For $q_{H,EH}$ the baseline value is zero, but we can define

$$q_{H,EH}(EC_{10}) = 0.1 \times q_{H,EH_{max}} \quad (S6)$$

Therefore:

$$EC_{10}(q_{E,N}) = \frac{\log(q_{E,N}(EC_{10})) - \log(q_{E,N}(0))}{k_{q_{E,N}}} \quad (S7)$$

$$EC_{10}(q_{EH,H}) = \frac{q_{EH,H}(EC_{10}) - q_{EH,H}(0)}{k_{q_{EH,H}}} \quad (S8)$$

$$EC_{10}(q_{N,E}) = \frac{\log(q_{N,E}(EC_{10})) - \log(q_{N,E}(0))}{k_{q_{N,E}}} \quad (S9)$$

$$EC_{10}(q_{N,C}) = \frac{q_{N,C}(EC_{10}) - q_{N,C}(0)}{k_{q_{N,C}}} \quad (S10)$$

$$EC_{10}(q_{E,C}) = \frac{q_{E,C}(EC_{10}) - q_{E,C}(0)}{k_{q_{E,C}}} \quad (S11)$$

$$EC_{10}(q_{H,EH}) = \sqrt[n]{\frac{q_{H,EH}(EC_{10}) \times EC_{50}^n}{q_{H,EH_{max}} - q_{H,EH}(EC_{10})}} \quad (S12)$$

Table S6. Effect concentrations (EC), no effect concentration (NOEC) and lowest effect concentration (LOEC) of all effects caused by valproic acid in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) embryos after 120 h of exposure. Those were derived only on the basis of data at time 120 hpf.

Effects	NOEC (µM)	LOEC (µM)	EC ₁₀ (µM)	EC ₅₀ (µM)
Coagulation	12.5	400	88	335
Pericardial edemata	25	50	38	90
Yolk edemata	12.5	25	82	<i>n.d.</i>
Yolk sac absorption reduced	12.5	25	20	194
Reduced heartbeat	200	400	209	<i>n.d.</i>
Blood congestion	100	200	119	<i>n.d.</i>
Scoliosis/lordosis	6.25	50	59	230
Craniofacial deformation	50	100	52	142
Small eyes	200	400	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>
Jitter/tremor	50	100	82	196
Development retardation	200	400	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>
Lack of hatch	200	400	300	<i>n.d.</i>

Those estimates were obtained with ToxRat Professional version 2.10.03 (ToxRat Solutions, Alsdorf, Germany) on the basis of the total number of affected embryos per test concentration at 120 hpf. For calculating EC values concentration 800 µM was excluded for all effects except for coagulation (death).

n.d.: Not determined (> highest test concentration)

Section 5 – Comparing R package *msm* and *GNU MCSim* results for CAV

We used the coronary allograft vasculopathy (CAV) multistate model and data described in Jackson and available in the *msm* R package (Jackson, C.H., 2011. Multi-State Models for Panel Data: The *msm* Package for R. J. Stat. Soft. 38. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v038.i08>). Figure S9 shows the parameter samples obtained by MCMC sampling with *GNU MCSim*, superimposed with the maximum likelihood and confidence interval obtained by bootstrapping with *msm*. *GNU MCSim* took 20 minutes to obtain 2000 MCMC samples, and *msm* took 1 hour to obtain 1000 bootstrap samples. The convergence of the MCMC chains is very fast. *GNU MCSim* MCMCs and *msm* bootstrapping are in complete agreement. The normal (Hessian) approximation of the 95% confidence intervals of *msm* can be large over-estimates (see q24).

Figure S10. Parameter trajectories of two MCMC runs of the coronary allograft vasculopathy model with *GNU MCSim* (red and blue) and R *msm* estimates (MLE, thick dashed line; 95% confidence intervals, normal approximation, long dashes; 95% confidence intervals, bootstrapped, short dashes).

Section 6 – Model code and executable MCMC file

1 Model code

```
# 5 compartment multistate model
# Considered states: Normal (N), Hatched (H), Effects (E),
#                   Coagulated (EC) and Hatched with Effects (EH)
# Hatching time estimated with piecewise constant model to fit the hatching rate
# Coupling to PK.

# Nominal values for parameters
# Units:
# Concentration: Mol
# Time: day
# Rates: 1/day

# States are the number of zebrafish embryo in each state, they can be output
States = {P_N_N, # Probability to stay in no effect state
         P_E_E, # ..... effects state
         P_H_H, # ..... hatched state
         P_EH_EH, # ..... hatched with effects state
         P_N_H, # ..... go from normal to hatched state
         P_N_E, # ..... effects state
         P_N_C, # ..... coagulated state
         P_N_EH, # ..... hatched with effects state
         P_E_C, # ..... effects to coagulated state
         P_E_N, # ..... effects to normal state
         P_E_H, # ..... hatched state
         P_E_EH, # ..... hatched with effects state
         P_H_EH, # ..... hatched to hatched with effects state
         P_EH_H}; # ..... hatched with effects to hatched state
Inputs = {q_N_H, q_E_EH};
Outputs = {N_N_t,
          N_H_t,
          N_E_t,
          N_C_t,
          N_EH_t,
          Mass_Balance, # Mass balance of the model
          LL_N_N,
          LL_H_H,
          LL_EH_EH,
          LL_E_E,
          LL_N_E,
          LL_N_H,
          LL_N_C,
          LL_N_EH,
          LL_E_C,
          LL_E_N,
          LL_E_H,
          LL_E_EH,
          LL_H_EH,
          LL_EH_H,
          q_E_N, # Transition rate from effects to normal state (/day)
          q_EH_H, # Transition rate from hatched with effects to hatched (/day)
          q_H_EH, # Transition rate from hatched to hatched with effects (/day)
          q_N_E, # Transition rate from Normal to effects state (/day)
          q_N_C, # Transition rate from Normal to coagulated state (/day)
          q_E_C}; # Transition rate from effects to coagulated state (/day)

# Parameters

# Concentration of chemical (M)
Dose; # in fact, nominal medium concentration
Conc_t; # time-varying concentration, will be calculated in ADDME.c
Conc_num = 21; # the line to read in concentration ratio input file

# Piecewise model parameters to fit the hatching rate
```

```

# Transition rate from Normal to hatched state (/day)
q_N_H_est;
# Transition rate from Effects to hatched with effects state (/day)
q_E_EH_est;
# Hatching time (day)
th;

# Statistical parameters
SD_qNH;
SD_qEEH;
SD_th;

# Transition rate from Normal to normal state (/day)
q_N_N;

# Transition rate from effects to effects state (/day)
q_E_E;

# Transition rate from hatched to hatched state (/day)
q_H_H;

# Transition rate from hatched with effects to hatched with effects state (/day)
q_EH_EH;

## Parameters needed to model relationships between transition rates and conc.
# q_E_N
qEN_zero;
k_qEN;

# q_EH_H
qEHH_zero;
k_qEHH;
u;
v;

# q_H_EH
qHEH_max;
qHEH_Hill;
qHEH_EC50;
qHEH_zero;
k_qHEH;

# q_N_E
qNE_zero;
k_qNE;

# q_N_C
qNC_zero;
k_qNC;

# q_E_C
qEC_zero;
k_qEC;

# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0;

# Number of zebrafish embryo with effects at time 0
N_H_t0;

# Number of zebrafish embryo with effects at time 0
N_E_t0;

# Number of zebrafish embryo coagulated at time 0
N_C_t0;

# Number of zebrafish embryo hatched with effects at time 0
N_EH_t0;

```

```

# Data: number of transitions
N_transitions;

#-----
# Dynamics
#-----

Dynamics {

  # Conc_t is time dependent and given by the PK model
  # We calculate it in the ADDME.c extension file:
  Inline( \#include "ADDME_v2.c" );

  # Transition rate from normal to effects state (/day)
  q_E_N = qEN_zero * exp(k_qEN * Conc_t);

  # Transition rate from hatched with effects to hatched state (/day)
  qEHH_zero = -u; # donc entre 0 et 4
  k_qEHH = v / 0.02; # donc entre -qEH_H_0 / 0.02 et 0, donc qEH,H > 0
  q_EH_H = qEHH_zero + k_qEHH * Conc_t;

  # Transition rate from hatched to hatched with effects state (/day)
  q_H_EH = (qHEH_max * pow(Conc_t, qHEH_Hill)) /
            (pow(qHEH_EC50, qHEH_Hill) + pow(Conc_t, qHEH_Hill));
  #q_H_EH = qHEH_zero * exp(k_qHEH * Conc_t);

  # Transition rate from Normal to effects state (/day)
  q_N_E = qNE_zero * exp(k_qNE * Conc_t);

  # Transition rate from Normal to coagulated state (/day)
  q_N_C = qNC_zero + k_qNC * Conc_t;

  # Transition rate from effects to coagulated state (/day)
  q_E_C = qEC_zero + k_qEC * Conc_t;

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to stay in no effect state
  dt(P_N_N) = - P_N_N * (q_N_H + q_N_E + q_N_C) + P_N_E * q_E_N;

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to go from normal to hatched state
  dt(P_N_H) = P_N_N * q_N_H - P_N_H * q_H_EH + P_N_EH * q_EH_H;

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to go from normal to effects state
  dt(P_N_E) = P_N_N * q_N_E - P_N_E * (q_E_N + q_E_C + q_E_EH);

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to go from normal to coagulated state
  dt(P_N_C) = P_N_N * q_N_C + P_N_E * q_E_C;

  # Probability to go from normal to hatched with effects state
  dt(P_N_EH) = P_N_H * q_H_EH + P_N_E * q_E_EH - P_N_EH * q_EH_H;

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to stay in hatched state
  dt(P_H_H) = - P_H_H * q_H_EH + P_H_EH * q_EH_H;

  # Probability to go from hatched to hatched with effects state
  dt(P_H_EH) = P_H_H * q_H_EH - P_H_EH * q_EH_H;

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to go from effects to hatched state
  dt(P_E_H) = P_E_N * q_N_H - P_E_H * q_H_EH + P_E_EH * q_EH_H;

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to go from effects to normal state
  dt(P_E_N) = - P_E_N * (q_N_H + q_N_E + q_N_C) + P_E_E * q_E_N;

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to stay in effects state
  dt(P_E_E) = P_E_N * q_N_E - P_E_E * (q_E_N + q_E_C + q_E_EH);

  # Probability of zebrafish embryo to go from effects to coagulated state

```

```

dt(P_E_C) = P_E_N * q_N_C + P_E_E * q_E_C;

# Probability to go from effects to hatched with effects state
dt(P_E_EH) = P_E_H * q_H_EH + P_E_E * q_E_EH - P_E_EH * q_EH_H;

# Probability to go from hatched with effects to hatched state
dt(P_EH_H) = - P_EH_H * q_H_EH + P_EH_EH * q_EH_H;

# Probability of zebrafish embryo to stay in hatched with effects state
dt(P_EH_EH) = P_EH_H * q_H_EH - P_EH_EH * q_EH_H;

}

#-----
# CalcOutputs
#-----

CalcOutputs {

# Probability to have N_x_t ZFE in state x at time t,
# if there are N_n_t0 ZFE in state n at time 0
N_N_t = N_N_t0 * P_N_N + N_E_t0 * P_E_N;
N_H_t = N_N_t0 * P_N_H + N_H_t0 * P_H_H + N_E_t0 * P_E_H + N_EH_t0 * P_EH_H;
N_E_t = N_N_t0 * P_N_E + N_E_t0 * P_E_E;
N_C_t = N_N_t0 * P_N_C + N_E_t0 * P_E_C + N_C_t0; # P_C_C = 1
N_EH_t = N_N_t0 * P_N_EH + N_H_t0 * P_H_EH + N_E_t0 * P_E_EH + N_EH_t0 * P_EH_EH;

# Mass balance
Mass_Balance = P_N_N + P_N_H + P_N_E + P_N_C + P_N_EH +
                P_E_C + P_E_N + P_E_EH + P_E_E + P_E_H +
                P_H_EH + P_H_H + P_EH_H + P_EH_EH;

# Likelihoods
LL_N_N = N_transitions * log((P_N_N > 0 ? P_N_N : 1E-30));
LL_N_H = N_transitions * log((P_N_H > 0 ? P_N_H : 1E-30));
LL_N_E = N_transitions * log((P_N_E > 0 ? P_N_E : 1E-30));
LL_N_C = N_transitions * log((P_N_C > 0 ? P_N_C : 1E-30));
LL_N_EH = N_transitions * log((P_N_EH > 0 ? P_N_EH : 1E-30));
LL_E_C = N_transitions * log((P_E_C > 0 ? P_E_C : 1E-30));
LL_E_N = N_transitions * log((P_E_N > 0 ? P_E_N : 1E-30));
LL_E_EH = N_transitions * log((P_E_EH > 0 ? P_E_EH : 1E-30));
LL_E_E = N_transitions * log((P_E_E > 0 ? P_E_E : 1E-30));
LL_E_H = N_transitions * log((P_E_H > 0 ? P_E_H : 1E-30));
LL_H_EH = N_transitions * log((P_H_EH > 0 ? P_H_EH : 1E-30));
LL_H_H = N_transitions * log((P_H_H > 0 ? P_H_H : 1E-30));
LL_EH_H = N_transitions * log((P_EH_H > 0 ? P_EH_H : 1E-30));
LL_EH_EH = N_transitions * log((P_EH_EH > 0 ? P_EH_EH : 1E-30));

} # End of output calculation

```

End.

2 PK link file

```

/* file containing code to read a concentration vs time profile and
interpolate it.
V2: pH change with dose, and so do concentration ratios,
so read directly the internal concentration for the correct dose.
*/

#define NCONCS 8
#define NTIMES 121

static int firstcall = 1;
static double C_read[NCONCS][NTIMES];
FILE* fp;
int i, j;
int Cindex, Tindex;
double Conc_t1, Conc_t2;

```

```

if (firstcall == 1) { /* on first call, read the concentration file */
    firstcall = 0; /* don't do it again */
    if (!(fp = fopen("VPA_internal.txt", "r"))) {
        printf("Error: file VPA_internal.txt not found - Exiting.\n\n");
        exit(0);
    }
    for (j = 0; j < NTIMES; j++) {
        C_read[0][j] = 0; /* at expoure zero, internal dose is always 0 */
    }
    for (i = 1; i < NCONCS; i++) {
        printf("reading concentration profiles #%d\n", i+1);
        for (j = 0; j < NTIMES; j++) {
            if ( fscanf(fp, "%lg", &(C_read[i][j])) == EOF ) {
                printf ("Error: VPA_internal.txt file too short - Exiting\n\n");
                exit(0);
            }
            else { /* reading ok */
                /* printf("C[%d,%d] = %g\n", i, j, C_read[i][j]); */
            }
        }
    }
} /* for i */
} /* end of on first call */

/* Find the position of current Dose in the official list of 8 doses */
double Ref_concs[NCONCS] = {0.000, 6.25E-6, 12.5E-6, 25.E-6,
                            50E-6, 100.E-6, 200.E-6, 400E-6};

for (i = 1; i < NCONCS; i++) {
    if (Dose < Ref_concs[i]) break;
}
Cindex = i-1;

/* Find the position of current time in the C_read array.
   There are 121 times from 0 to 5 days by increments of 1/24.0 */
Tindex = (int) ((*pdTime) * 24);

/* Compute concentration at current time by interpolation on the lower bound
   of Concentration */
if (Tindex < (NTIMES - 1))
    Conc_t1 = C_read[Cindex][Tindex] +
              (C_read[Cindex][Tindex + 1] - C_read[Cindex][Tindex]) *
              ((*pdTime) * 24 - Tindex);
else /* at time boundary */
    Conc_t1 = C_read[Cindex][Tindex];

/* Compute concentration at current time by interpolation on the upper bound
   of Concentration */
if (Cindex < (NCONCS - 1)) {
    if (Tindex < (NTIMES - 1))
        Conc_t2 = C_read[Cindex+1][Tindex] +
                  (C_read[Cindex+1][Tindex + 1] - C_read[Cindex+1][Tindex]) *
                  ((*pdTime) * 24 - Tindex);
    else /* at time boundary */
        Conc_t2 = C_read[Cindex+1][Tindex];
}
else { /* at concentration boundary */
    if (Tindex < (NTIMES - 1))
        Conc_t2 = C_read[Cindex][Tindex] +
                  (C_read[Cindex][Tindex + 1] - C_read[Cindex][Tindex]) *
                  ((*pdTime) * 24 - Tindex);
    else /* time boundary */
        Conc_t2 = C_read[Cindex][Tindex];
}

/* Interpolate between the two concentrations calculated above; Conc_t will be
   used in the multistate model */
if (Cindex < (NCONCS - 1)) {

```

```

    Conc_t = Conc_t1 + (Conc_t2 - Conc_t1) *
                (Dose - Ref_concs[Cindex]) /
                (Ref_concs[Cindex+1] - Ref_concs[Cindex]);
}
else {
    Conc_t = Conc_t1;
}

/* End */

```

3 MCMC input file

```

# Input file for MCMC calibration of the coupled PBPK-multistate model with
# valproic acid data.

Integrate(Lsodes, 1E-7, 1E-9, 0);
MCMC("q_vs_Dose_coupledPK_mcmc_1.out", "", "", 30000, 0, 1, 30000, 564523);

Level { # Pop
  ## Piecewise constant model parameters
  Distrib(q_N_H_est, Uniform, 0, 20);
  Distrib(q_E_EH_est, Uniform, 0, 10);
  Distrib(th, Uniform, 1, 5);

  # Transition rate from effects to normal state (/day)
  Distrib(qEN_zero, Uniform, 0, 2);
  Distrib(k_qEN, Uniform, -6E2, 0); # lb divided by 2 for PK conc. adjustment

  # Transition rate from hatched with effects to hatched state (/day)
  # Distrib(qEHH_zero, Uniform, 1, 4);
  # Distrib(k_qEHH, Uniform, -3E2, -1E2); # lb divided by 2 for PK conc. adjustment
  Distrib(u, Uniform, -4, 0);
  Distrib(v, Uniform, u, 0);

  # Transition rate from hatched to hatched with effects state (/day)
  Distrib(qHEH_max, Uniform, 0, 40); # ub divided by 2 for PK conc. adjustment
  Distrib(qHEH_Hill, Uniform, 0, 15);
  Distrib(qHEH_EC50, Uniform, 0, 0.01); # lb divided by 4 and ub by 2 for PK conc.
adjustment
  #Distrib(qHEH_zero, Uniform, 0, 0.4);
  #Distrib(k_qHEH, Uniform, 0, 400);

  # Transition rate from normal to effects state (/day)
  Distrib(qNE_zero, Uniform, 0, 0.06);
  Distrib(k_qNE, Uniform, 2E2, 4.5E2); # lb divided by 4 and ub by 2 for PK conc.
adjustment

  # Transition rate from normal to coagulated state (/day)
  Distrib(qNC_zero, Uniform, 0, 0.01);
  Distrib(k_qNC, Uniform, 0, 10); # ub divided by 2 for PK conc. adjustment

  # Transition rate from effects to coagulated state (/day)
  Distrib(qEC_zero, Uniform, 0, 0.1);
  Distrib(k_qEC, Uniform, 0, 10); # ub divided by 2 for PK conc. adjustment

  Distrib(SD_qNH, TruncNormal, 1.1, 0.5, 1.01, 10);
  Distrib(SD_qEEH, TruncNormal, 1.1, 0.5, 1.01, 10);
  Distrib(SD_th, TruncNormal, 1.1, 0.5, 1.01, 10);

  # Initial conditions
  # Probability of embryo to stay in no effect state during time t+dt=0
  P_N_N = 1;
  # Probability of embryo to stay in hatched state during time t+dt=0
  P_H_H = 1;
  # Probability of embryo to stay in effects state during time t+dt=0
  P_E_E = 1;

```

```

# Probability of embryo to stay in coagulated state during time t+dt=0
# P_C_C = 1;
# Probability of embryo to stay in hatched with effects during time t+dt=0
P_EH_EH = 1;

Level { # all doses

Distrib(th, TruncLogNormal, th, SD_th, 0, 5);
Distrib(q_N_H_est, LogNormal, q_N_H_est, SD_qNH);
Distrib(q_E_EH_est, LogNormal, q_E_EH_est, SD_qEEH);

Level { # Dose 0 Mol
Dose = 0;
# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0 = 120;
Level { # transition N -> N
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 117 transitions N -> N
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 117;
Print (LL_N_N, 1);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 112 transitions N -> N
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 112;
Print (LL_N_N, 2);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 42 transitions N -> N
StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 42;
Print (LL_N_N, 3);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition N -> N
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 1;
Print (LL_N_N, 4);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 5);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}

```

```

}
}
Level { # transition N -> C
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 1);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 2);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 3);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 4);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 5);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 3 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 3;
  Print (LL_N_E, 1);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
}

```

```

Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 5 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 5;
  Print (LL_N_E, 2);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 3);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 4);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 5);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> H
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 1);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 2);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));

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Simulation { # day 3: 70 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 70;
  Print (LL_N_H, 3);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 4: 38 transitions N -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 38;
    Print (LL_N_H, 4);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 5 transitions N -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 5;
    Print (LL_N_H, 5);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 3 transitions N -> EH
    StartTime(3);

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    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> E
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 1);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 3 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_E_E, 2);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 4 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 4;
    Print (LL_E_E, 3);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 2 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_E, 4);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 2 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);

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    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_E, 5);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 1);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 2);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 3);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 72 transitions H -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 72;
    Print (LL_H_H, 4);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 106 transitions H -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 106;
    Print (LL_H_H, 5);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> C
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}

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    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 2);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 3);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 4);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 5);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> N
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 1);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 2);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}

```

```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 3);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 4);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 5);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {

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```

Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 1 transition H -> EH

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StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 1;
Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> EH
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition EH -> EH
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 1;
Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 3 transitions EH -> EH
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 3;
Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

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    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 3 transitions EH -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> H
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 1);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
}
}

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```

    Print (LL_E_H, 2);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 3 transitions E -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 3;
  Print (LL_E_H, 3);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition E -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_H, 4);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 5);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
} # End level dose 0 Mol

Level { # Dose 6.25E-6 Mol (1 mg/L)
Dose = 6.25E-6;
# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0 = 60;
Level { # transition N -> N
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 60 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 60;
  Print (LL_N_N, 1);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 53 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 53;
  Print (LL_N_N, 2);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 24 transitions N -> N

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StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 24;
Print (LL_N_N, 3);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 4);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 5);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> C
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> C
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_C, 1);
Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_C, 2);
Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_C, 3);
Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

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    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 4);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 5);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 1);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 7 transitions N -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 7;
    Print (LL_N_E, 2);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 3);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 4);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
}
}

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Print (LL_N_E, 5);
Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> H
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 1);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 2);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 29 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 29;
  Print (LL_N_H, 3);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 25 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 25;
  Print (LL_N_H, 4);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 5);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}

```

```

}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> E
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 1);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 2);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
}

```

```

Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 4 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 4;
  Print (LL_E_E, 3);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 4);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 5);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 1);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 2);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 3);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));

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Simulation { # day 4: 31 transitions H -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 31;
  Print (LL_H_H, 4);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 60 transitions H -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 60;
  Print (LL_H_H, 5);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> C
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 1);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 2);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 3);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 4);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(4);

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    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 5);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> N
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 1);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 2);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> N
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_E_N, 3);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 4);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 5);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);

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    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
}
}

```

```

    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition EH -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
  }
}

```

```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {

```

```

Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> H
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 1);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 2);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 2 transitions E -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 2;
  Print (LL_E_H, 3);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 4 transitions E -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 4;
  Print (LL_E_H, 4);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 5);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
} # End level dose 6.25E-6 Mol (1 mg/L)

Level { # Dose 12.5E-6 Mol (2 mg/L)

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Dose = 12.5E-6;
# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0 = 60;
Level { # transition N -> N
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 1: 60 transitions N -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 60;
    Print (LL_N_N, 1);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 2: 58 transitions N -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 58;
    Print (LL_N_N, 2);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 3: 26 transitions N -> N
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 26;
    Print (LL_N_N, 3);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> N
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_N, 4);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> N
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_N, 5);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition N -> C
  Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 1);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
  }
}

```

```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 2);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 3);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 4);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 5);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 1);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 2 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 2;
  Print (LL_N_E, 2);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {

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```

Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition N -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_N_E, 3);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 4);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 5);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> H
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 1);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 2);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 30 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 30;
  Print (LL_N_H, 3);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 25 transitions N -> H

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StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 25;
Print (LL_N_H, 4);
Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> H
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_H, 5);
Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition N -> EH
StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 1;
Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition N -> EH
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 1;
Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

```

```

    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> E
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 1);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 2);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 3);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 4);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 5);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;

```

```

    Print (LL_H_H, 1);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 2);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 3);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 31 transitions H -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 31;
  Print (LL_H_H, 4);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 57 transitions H -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 57;
  Print (LL_H_H, 5);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> C
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 1);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 2);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}

```

```

}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 3);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 4);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 5);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> N
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 1);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 2);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 3);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
}

```

```

Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 4);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 5);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));

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Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition EH -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(0);

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    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);

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    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 3 transitions EH -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> H
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 1);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 2);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 2 transitions E -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_H, 3);
}
}

```

```

    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition E -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_E_H, 4);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 5);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
} # End level dose 12.5E-6 Mol (2 mg/L)

Level { # Dose 25E-6 Mol (4 mg/L)
  Dose = 25E-6;
  # Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
  N_N_t0 = 60;
  Level { # transition N -> N
    Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
    Simulation { # day 1: 59 transitions N -> N
      StartTime(0);
      q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
      q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
      N_transitions = 59;
      Print (LL_N_N, 1);
      Data (LL_N_N, 1);
    }
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 2: 55 transitions N -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 55;
    Print (LL_N_N, 2);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 3: 24 transitions N -> N
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 24;
    Print (LL_N_N, 3);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> N
    StartTime(3);

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    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_N, 4);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> N
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_N, 5);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> C
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 1 transition N -> C
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_N_C, 1);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 2);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 3);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 4);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);

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    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 5);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 1);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 4 transitions N -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 4;
    Print (LL_N_E, 2);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 3);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 4);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 5);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> H
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}

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```

    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 2);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 3: 31 transitions N -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 31;
    Print (LL_N_H, 3);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 4: 24 transitions N -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 24;
    Print (LL_N_H, 4);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 5);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}

```

```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 2 transitions N -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 2;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> E
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 1);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 2);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_E, 3);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {

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Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition E -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_E, 4);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 1 transition E -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_E, 5);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 1);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 2);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 3);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 31 transitions H -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 31;
  Print (LL_H_H, 4);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 55 transitions H -> H

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    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 55;
    Print (LL_H_H, 5);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> C
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 1);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 2);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 3);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 4);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 5);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> N
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

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    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 1);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 2);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 2 transitions E -> N
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_N, 3);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 4);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 5);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
}
}

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    Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}

```

```

}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> EH
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
}

```

```

Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 1 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 2 transitions EH -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 2;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> H
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));

```

```

Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 1);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 2);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 3);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 4);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 5);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
} # End level dose 25E-6 Mol (4 mg/L)

Level { # Dose 50E-6 Mol (7 mg/L)
Dose = 50E-6;
# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0 = 60;
Level { # transition N -> N
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 59 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 59;
  Print (LL_N_N, 1);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
}

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```

}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 54 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 54;
  Print (LL_N_N, 2);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 31 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 31;
  Print (LL_N_N, 3);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition N -> N
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_N_N, 4);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 1 transition N -> N
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_N_N, 5);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> C
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 1 transition N -> C
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_N_C, 1);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 2);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
}

```

```

Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 3);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 4);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 5);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 1);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 5 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 5;
  Print (LL_N_E, 2);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 4 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 4;
  Print (LL_N_E, 3);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));

```

```

Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 4);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 5);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> H
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 1);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 2);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 18 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 18;
  Print (LL_N_H, 3);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 22 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 22;
  Print (LL_N_H, 4);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(4);

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    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 5);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 8 transitions N -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 8;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> E
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);

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    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 1);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 2);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> E
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_E_E, 3);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition E -> E
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_E_E, 4);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 5);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 1);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 2);
}
}

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```

    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 3);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 4: 16 transitions H -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 16;
    Print (LL_H_H, 4);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 34 transitions H -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 34;
    Print (LL_H_H, 5);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> C
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 1);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 2);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 3);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}

```

```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 4);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 5);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> N
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 1);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 2);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 3);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 4);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {

```

```

Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 5);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 2 transitions E -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 2;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 1 transition E -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH

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    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 5 transitions H -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 5;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 6 transitions H -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 6;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> EH
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

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    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);;
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 2 transitions EH -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 8 transitions EH -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 8;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
}
}

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Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 9 transitions EH -> H
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 9;
Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> H
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_E_H, 1);
Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_E_H, 2);
Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 3 transitions E -> H
StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 3;
Print (LL_E_H, 3);
Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 2 transitions E -> H
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 2;
Print (LL_E_H, 4);
Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}

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}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 5);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
} # End level dose 50E-6 Mol (7 mg/L)

Level { # Dose 100E-6 Mol (14 mg/L)
Dose = 100E-6;
# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0 = 60;
Level { # transition N -> N
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 57 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 57;
  Print (LL_N_N, 1);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 50 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 50;
  Print (LL_N_N, 2);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 25 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 25;
  Print (LL_N_N, 3);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> N
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_N, 4);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> N
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

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    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_N, 5);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> C
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 1);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 2);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 3);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 4);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 5);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 3 transitions N -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
}
}

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```

Print (LL_N_E, 1);
Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 7 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 7;
  Print (LL_N_E, 2);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 3 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 3;
  Print (LL_N_E, 3);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition N -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_N_E, 4);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_E, 5);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> H
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 1);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 2);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}

```

```

}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 15 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 15;
  Print (LL_N_H, 3);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 14 transitions N -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 14;
  Print (LL_N_H, 4);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 5);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 7 transitions N -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 7;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
}

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```

Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 10 transitions N -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 10;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> E
  Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 1);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
  Simulation { # day 2: 3 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_E_E, 2);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
  Simulation { # day 3: 4 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 4;
    Print (LL_E_E, 3);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
  Simulation { # day 4: 3 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_E_E, 4);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));

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Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 5);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 1);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 2);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_H, 3);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 4: 3 transitions H -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_H_H, 4);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 2 transitions H -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_H_H, 5);
    Data (LL_H_H, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> C
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(0);

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    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 1);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 2);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 3);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 4);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 2 transitions E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_C, 5);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> N
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 1);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
}
}

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    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 2);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 3);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 4);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 5);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 4 transitions E -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 4;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
}
}

```

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    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 4 transitions E -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 4;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 5: 2 transitions E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 14 transitions H -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 14;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}

```

```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 15 transitions H -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 15;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> EH
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 11 transitions EH -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 11;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 37 transitions EH -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 37;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H

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Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 2 transitions EH -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 2;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
}
Level { # transition E -> H
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 1);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H

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    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 2);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 2 transitions E -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_H, 3);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 4);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 5);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
} # End level dose 100E-6 Mol (14 mg/L)

Level { # Dose 200E-6 Mol (29 mg/L)
Dose = 200E-6;
# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0 = 60;
Level { # transition N -> N
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 50 transitions N -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 50;
    Print (LL_N_N, 1);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 38 transitions N -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 38;
    Print (LL_N_N, 2);
    Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}

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```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 19 transitions N -> N
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 19;
  Print (LL_N_N, 3);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> N
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_N, 4);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> N
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_N, 5);
  Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> C
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 1);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 2);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 3);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {

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```

Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 4);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_C, 5);
  Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 10 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 10;
  Print (LL_N_E, 1);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 12 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 12;
  Print (LL_N_E, 2);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 14 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 14;
  Print (LL_N_E, 3);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 4 transitions N -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 4;
  Print (LL_N_E, 4);
  Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E

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    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 5);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> H
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 1);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 2);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 8 transitions N -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 8;
    Print (LL_N_H, 3);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 4);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 5);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

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    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 15 transitions N -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 15;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> E
  Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_E, 1);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
  Simulation { # day 2: 6 transitions E -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 6;
  }
}

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    Print (LL_E_E, 2);
    Data (LL_E_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 16 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 16;
  Print (LL_E_E, 3);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 2 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 2;
  Print (LL_E_E, 4);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 3 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 3;
  Print (LL_E_E, 5);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 1);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 2);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 3);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}

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}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 4);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition H -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_H, 5);
  Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> C
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 1);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 2);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 3);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> C
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_C, 4);
  Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
}

```

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Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 5);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> N
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 1);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 2: 4 transitions E -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 4;
    Print (LL_E_N, 2);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 3);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 4);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 5);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));

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Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 3: 2 transitions E -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 2;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 4: 28 transitions E -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 28;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
  Simulation { # day 5: 3 transitions E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(1);

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    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 8 transitions H -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 8;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition H -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> EH
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);

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    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 3 transitions EH -> EH
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 3;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 54 transitions EH -> EH
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 54;
    Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
    Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
}
}

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```

    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition EH -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
    Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition E -> H
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 1);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 2);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 3);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 4);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 5);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}

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}
} # End level dose 200E-6 Mol (29 mg/L)

Level { # Dose 400E-6 Mol (58 mg/L)
Dose = 400E-6;
# Number of zebrafish embryo with no effect at time 0
N_N_t0 = 60;
Level { # transition N -> N
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 1);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 2);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 3);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 4);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> N
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_N_N, 5);
Data (LL_N_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> C
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> C
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);

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    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 1);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 2);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 3);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 4);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_C, 5);
    Data (LL_N_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> E
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 60 transitions N -> E
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 60;
    Print (LL_N_E, 1);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 2);
}
}

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    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 3);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 4);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_E));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> E
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_E, 5);
    Data (LL_N_E, 1);
  }
}
Level { # transition N -> H
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 1);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 2);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
  Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> H
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_N_H, 3);
    Data (LL_N_H, 1);
  }
}

```

```

}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 4);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_H, 5);
  Data (LL_N_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition N -> EH
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {

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Likelihood (LL_N_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_N_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition N -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_N_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_N_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> E
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> E
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_E, 1);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 2: 59 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 59;
  Print (LL_E_E, 2);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 3: 57 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 57;
  Print (LL_E_E, 3);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 4: 34 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 34;
  Print (LL_E_E, 4);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_E, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_E));
Simulation { # day 5: 29 transitions E -> E
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 29;
  Print (LL_E_E, 5);
  Data (LL_E_E, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> H
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> H

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StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_H_H, 1);
Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> H
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_H_H, 2);
Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> H
StartTime(2);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_H_H, 3);
Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition H -> H
StartTime(3);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_H_H, 4);
Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition H -> H
StartTime(4);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_H_H, 5);
Data (LL_H_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> C
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> C
StartTime(0);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
N_transitions = 0;
Print (LL_E_C, 1);
Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 2: 1 transition E -> C
StartTime(1);
q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);

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    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_E_C, 2);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> C
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 1;
    Print (LL_E_C, 3);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 4: 18 transitions E -> C
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 18;
    Print (LL_E_C, 4);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_C, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_C));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> C
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_C, 5);
    Data (LL_E_C, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> N
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(0);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 1);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(1);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_N, 2);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> N
    StartTime(2);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
}
}

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    Print (LL_E_N, 3);
    Data (LL_E_N, 1);
  }
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 4);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_N, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_N));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> N
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_N, 5);
  Data (LL_E_N, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> EH
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 1 transition E -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 5 transitions E -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 5;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}

```

```

}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 5 transitions E -> C
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 5;
  Print (LL_E_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_E_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition H -> EH
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_H_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_H_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition H -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_H_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_H_EH, 1);
}
}
}

```

```

Level { # transition EH -> EH
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 1);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 2);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 3);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 4: 1 transition EH -> EH
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 1;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_EH, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_EH));
Simulation { # day 5: 6 transitions EH -> EH
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 6;
  Print (LL_EH_EH, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_EH, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition EH -> H
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 1);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));

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Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 2);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(2);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 3);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(3);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 4);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_EH_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_EH_H));
Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition EH -> H
  StartTime(4);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_EH_H, 5);
  Data (LL_EH_H, 1);
}
}
Level { # transition E -> H
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 1: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(0);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 1);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 2: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(1);
  q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
  q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
  N_transitions = 0;
  Print (LL_E_H, 2);
  Data (LL_E_H, 1);
}
}
Level {
Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
Simulation { # day 3: 0 transition E -> H
  StartTime(2);

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```

    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 3);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 4: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(3);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 4);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
Level {
  Likelihood (LL_E_H, UserSpecifiedLL, Prediction(LL_E_H));
  Simulation { # day 5: 0 transition E -> H
    StartTime(4);
    q_N_H = NDoses(2, 0, q_N_H_est, 0, th);
    q_E_EH = NDoses(2, 0, q_E_EH_est, 0, th);
    N_transitions = 0;
    Print (LL_E_H, 5);
    Data (LL_E_H, 1);
  }
}
} # End level dose 400E-6 Mol (58 mg/L)
} # End all doses
} # End level pop

End.

```